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Emerging Diversity within Chrysophytes, Choanoflagellates and Bicosoecids Based on Molecular Surveys

Javier del Campo^{a,1}, Ramon Massana^a

^aDepartament de Biologia Marina i Oceanografia, Institut de Ciències del Mar, CSIC.
Passeig Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37-49, 08003 Barcelona, Spain

¹Corresponding author f: +34-93-2309555. e-mail: jdelcampo@icm.cat (J. del Campo).

Running title: Emerging Diversity Within Three Protist Group

23 In recent years, a substantial amount of data on aquatic protists has been obtained
24 from culture-independent molecular approaches, unveiling a large diversity and the
25 existence of new lineages. However, sequences affiliated with minor groups (in terms
26 of clonal abundance) have often been under analyzed, and this hides a potentially
27 relevant source of phylogenetic information. Here we have searched public
28 databases for 18S rDNA sequences of chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and
29 bicosoecids retrieved from molecular surveys of protists. These three groups are
30 often considered to account for most of the heterotrophic flagellates, an important
31 functional component in microbial food webs. They represented a significant fraction
32 of clones in freshwater studies, whereas their relative clonal abundance was low in
33 marine studies. The novelty displayed by this dataset was notable. Most
34 environmental sequences were distant to sequences of cultured organisms,
35 indicating a significant bias in the representation of taxa in culture. Moreover, they
36 were often distant to sequences from other molecular surveys, suggesting an
37 insufficient sequencing effort to characterize the in situ diversity of these groups.
38 Phylogenetic trees with complete sequences present the most accurate
39 representation of the diversity of these groups, with the emergence of several new
40 clades formed exclusively by environmental sequences. Exhaustive data mining in
41 sequence databases allowed the identification of new diversity hidden inside
42 chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and bicosoecids.

43 Key words: 18S rDNA; bicosoecids; choanoflagellates; chrysophytes; emerging
44 diversity; heterotrophic flagellates; maximum likelihood phylogeny; molecular
45 surveys.

46

46 Introduction

47 Heterotrophic Flagellates (HF) are distributed in planktonic environments at
48 concentrations between 10^2 and 10^5 cells ml^{-1} , representing 10-30% of protist cells in
49 upper marine waters (Jürgens and Massana 2008). HF cells are often phagotrophs
50 that graze and control the abundance of prokaryotes and picoeukaryotes (Pernthaler
51 2005), but also may include dispersal stages of parasites of other marine organisms
52 (Guillou et al. 2008). Consequently, HF are important actors in microbial food webs
53 and play key roles in global biogeochemical cycles (Sherr and Sherr 2002;
54 Chambouvet et al. 2008). Traditionally, the diversity of HF assemblages has been
55 studied by microscopy and culturing, yielding the impression that most cells belong to
56 chrysophytes, choanoflagellates or bicosoecids (Fenchel 1982; Arndt et al. 2000).
57 However, the in situ diversity and ecological relevance of these taxonomic groups
58 remain poorly investigated.

59 The chrysophytes is a large group of stramenopiles with about 100 described
60 genera (Lee et al. 2000). They include colorless cells (heterotrophs) and chloroplast-
61 containing cells (phototrophs or mixotrophs) with one or two flagella (Preisig et al.
62 1991). The majority lives in freshwater but there are also some well-known marine
63 species, such as *Paraphysomonas imperforata*. The phylogeny of chrysophytes
64 using 18S rDNA was presented by Andersen et al. (1999), and currently there are 30
65 genera represented in GenBank. The choanoflagellates are colorless ovoid cells with
66 about 50 genera described from marine, brackish and freshwater systems
67 (Leadbeater 1991; Lee et al. 2000). They have a collar surrounding a unique
68 flagellum, and some are covered by an intricate lorica. They belong to Opisthokonta

69 and are the closest metazoan relatives, thus attracting the interest of evolutionary
70 biologists (King et al. 2008). Their phylogeny using the 18S rDNA was presented in
71 Carr et al. (2008) and currently there are 16 genera in GenBank's Taxonomy.
72 Bicosoecids are colorless flagellates that belong to the Stramenopiles and include 11
73 genera (Lee et al. 2000; Cavalier-Smith and Chao 2006), all represented in
74 GenBank's Taxonomy with their 18S rDNA. Cells have typically two flagella. Both
75 marine and freshwater species are known, including the well-known marine species
76 *Cafeteria roenbergensis* (Fenchel et al. 1988).

77 Cultured strains have been essential for delineating the physiology and
78 phylogeny of the three groups (Leipe et al. 1994, Andersen et al. 1999; Cavalier-
79 Smith and Chao 2006), but it is not clear if these cultured strains are ecologically
80 relevant. For instance, a very low abundance of *Paraphysomonas imperforata* (Lim et
81 al. 1999) and *Cafeteria roenbergensis* (Massana et al. 2007) was recorded in
82 samples from which these two species were easily enriched. *In situ* diversity can be
83 better addressed by culture-independent molecular techniques (Caron et al. 2004).
84 Environmental 18S rDNA libraries targeting microbial eukaryotes highlighted new
85 lineages that appeared in most studies in high clonal abundance, such as MAST
86 (Marine Stramenopiles) (Massana et al. 2006) and MALV (Marine Alveolates)
87 (Guillou et al. 2008), whereas chrysophytes, choanoflagellates or bicosoecids were
88 generally represented by few sequences in marine (Massana and Pedrós-Alió 2008)
89 and freshwater (Lefranc et al. 2005; Richards et al. 2005; Slapeta et al. 2005)
90 individual studies. These later groups have been under analyzed due to their low
91 clonal abundance, and we hypothesize that new diversity would emerge once we put

92 together sequences from independent studies.

93 Here, we searched public databases (nucleotide collection nr/nt in GenBank)
94 for chrysophyte, choanoflagellate and bicosoecid 18S rDNA sequences obtained in
95 molecular surveys. We used this sequence dataset to pursue three goals. First, to
96 determine the clonal contribution of these groups in marine and freshwater systems.
97 Second, to analyze the sequence novelty within each group, i.e. the difference
98 between target sequences and those deposited in GenBank (both from cultured
99 strains or from other molecular surveys). This novelty can then be interpreted in
100 terms of sequencing effort and representation of taxa in culture. Third, to present a
101 robust phylogeny of each group combining all available sequences to better describe
102 their diversity and identify new clades formed by environmental sequences only.
103 These phylogenetic trees can serve as a backbone where to map tag sequences that
104 begin to appear by Next Generation Sequencing technologies (Amaral-Zettler et al.
105 2009; Stoeck et al. 2009). For each of the three taxonomic groups, major differences
106 are found in clonal abundance, novelty pattern and new diversity in marine and
107 freshwater systems.

108

109 **Results**

110 In order to obtain an exhaustive description of the phylogenetic diversity of
111 chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and bicosoecids, we screened GenBank and our
112 unpublished libraries to retrieve all sequences from these groups obtained in marine
113 and freshwater molecular surveys. The dataset inspected included 292

114 environmental clone libraries of 18S rDNA genes (representing more than 13000
115 sequences) that have been published in 58 scientific papers and targeted a large
116 variety of systems, depths in the water column, and physical-chemical settings
117 (Supplementary Table 1). Some studies focused on the smallest eukaryotic microbes
118 (<3-5 μm) and others to the whole water community. Overall, we obtained 230
119 chrysophyte, 89 choanoflagellate and 76 bicosoecid environmental sequences (listed
120 in the Supplementary Table 2). Sequences were grouped into two categories (marine
121 and freshwater) before further abundance, novelty and diversity analyses.

122 Relative Clonal Abundance in Environmental Surveys

123 The representation of chrysophyte, choanoflagellate and bicosoecid
124 sequences in 18S rDNA libraries was addressed considering only the studies that
125 reported the clonal abundance of distinct taxonomic groups (82 libraries published in
126 14 papers, Supplementary Table 3). In each library, clones were assigned to putative
127 heterotrophic flagellate (HF) groups, to putative phototrophic (PP) protist groups
128 (prasinophytes, dinoflagellates, haptophytes and others) and to other heterotrophic
129 protists (OHP) (ciliates and fungi). Then, the proportion of clones within different HF
130 groups was displayed (Fig. 1). Chrysophyte sequences appeared in most
131 environmental surveys, averaging 3.3% of HF clones in marine and 11.8% in
132 freshwater studies (Fig. 1). The relative clonal abundance of choanoflagellates
133 averaged 1.3% in marine and 3.7% in freshwater systems. Bicosoecids were rarely
134 found in marine surveys (0.6% relative clonal abundance on average) and were
135 rather abundant in freshwater systems (21.6% on average, in some cases up to
136 50%). The bulk of sequences from putative HF in marine systems affiliated with

137 MALV and MAST. In freshwater systems, other alveolates and cercozoans
138 accounted for a significant number of clones.

139 Novelty of Environmental Sequences

140 Figure 2 plots together two values obtained for each environmental sequence
141 after a GenBank search: the similarity against the closest environmental match
142 (CEM) and the similarity against the closest cultured match (CCM). Sequences
143 appeared widely distributed in the graph with each taxonomic group displaying a
144 distinct novelty pattern. Most chrysophyte sequences from marine samples
145 accumulated in two plot regions: those with high CEM-CCM similarity values (above
146 98%), thus similar to sequences from cultures and molecular surveys, and those with
147 high CEM (above 98%) and low CCM values (below 94%), thus similar only to
148 sequences from molecular surveys (Fig. 2A). Choanoflagellates sequences showed
149 a more uniform dispersion in the graph, with a tendency of freshwater sequences to
150 have lower values in both axis (Fig. 2B). Interestingly, we detected some sequences
151 that were very close to cultured species but had not been retrieved in other molecular
152 surveys (this did not occur in chrysophytes). The novelty pattern for bicosoecids also
153 showed a uniform dispersion of dots in the graph, as the previous example, but here
154 the difference between systems was very marked, with sequences from marine
155 environments being above 98% in both axis (Fig. 2C).

156 Averaging the similarity values against CEM and CCM for all sequences
157 yielded the novelty degree of a given dataset (Table 1). The difference between CCM
158 similarity and 100% represented the bias in representation of cultures, whereas the
159 difference between CEM similarity and 100% represented the bias in environmental

160 sequencing. Considering all sequences together yielded average similarities of 94-
161 95% in all cases (except chrysophytes against CEM). This general overview
162 obscured clear differences between systems, with choanoflagellates and bicosoecids
163 being significantly more novel in freshwater (91% similarity) than in marine systems
164 (95% and 98%, respectively). The difference between CEM and CCM similarity in
165 each row represented the increase of knowledge gained by environmental
166 sequencing. Surprisingly, in most cases both values were very similar. The only
167 exception was the marine chrysophytes, that showed significant differences between
168 both values (t-student test, $p < 0.0001$). Altogether, the novelty degree was larger in
169 freshwater than in marine systems.

170 Phylogenetic Trees and New Clades

171 Using complete 18S rDNA sequences, we constructed Maximum Likelihood
172 phylogenetic trees for chrysophytes (Fig. 3), choanoflagellates (Fig. 4) and
173 bicosoecids (Fig. 5). Environmental sequences appeared in the trees in different
174 color depending on their origin (blue: marine; green: freshwater), whereas reference
175 sequences from cultured organisms appeared in black. Trees were divided into
176 separate clades, some of them already defined in published trees and others being
177 new, derived from the present analysis. Clades always contained sequences from
178 different studies and were generally well supported by high Maximum Likelihood
179 bootstrap values. In addition, Neighbor Joining phylogenetic trees were done to
180 assign partial sequences to the clades delineated by complete sequences (trees not
181 shown). The total number of environmental sequences (complete and partial) within
182 each clade was shown in brackets after the clade name (in blue for marine and green

183 for freshwater sequences). Most clades contained environmental sequences.

184 The chrysophyte tree obtained here showed good agreement with the
185 topology described in Andersen et al. (1999), displaying the same clades A to F
186 defined there (although clade F was subdivided into two lineages in our tree) plus 4
187 additional new clades (Fig. 3). In general these clades presented ML bootstrap
188 values above 60%. Except clade A (Synurophyceae), the other eleven clades
189 incorporated environmental sequences. Clades B1, B2 and E contained only
190 freshwater representatives, whereas Clades C, D, F1 and F2 contained sequences
191 from both freshwater and marine systems. New chrysophyte clades described for
192 Lake George (Richards et al. 2005) belonged to clade C (LG-G and LG-H) and clade
193 F1 (LG-I). Many of the environmental sequences affiliated with the four new
194 chrysophyte clades. Clade G contained the Marine A group from Shi et al. (2009),
195 clones from different marine systems and also freshwater sequences from Lake
196 George. Clade I contained only marine sequences, including the ones belonging to
197 Shi's Marine B group. Clade H contained a monophyletic subclade of sequences
198 from marine samples, corresponding to Shi's Marine C group, together with
199 sequences from freshwater origin. Finally, clade J was formed by only few
200 sequences. Since clades G, H and I included sequences from both pigmented cells
201 (Shi et al. 2009) and putative heterotrophic cells growing in unamended dark
202 incubations (Massana et al. 2006), they preferentially included heterotrophic or
203 mixotrophic cells.

204 The emerging diversity observed in the choanoflagellate tree was also notable,
205 with two new clades (E and F) unveiled by environmental sequences (Fig. 4). All nine

206 defined clades were well supported by high ML bootstrap values (above 85%) and
207 included environmental sequences. Clade C (corresponding to clade 2 of Carr et al.
208 2008), contained sequences from freshwater origin only, whereas the rest of the
209 clades included only marine representatives. Carr's clade 1 was separated into
210 clades A and B, which are distantly related phylogenetically, and the remaining
211 clades would form Carr's clade 3.

212 The bicosoecid tree showed a clear separation between a large freshwater
213 clade and several marine clades, all supported by high ML bootstrap values (Fig. 5).
214 Most sequences retrieved from marine systems affiliated with the genera *Caecitellus*
215 and *Cafeteria*. The *Bicosoeca* cluster included sequences previously named as
216 MAST-13 (Zuendorf et al. 2006) that clearly belonged to bicosoecids in our
217 stramenopile tree (not shown) and in recent studies (Park and Simpson 2010). On
218 the other hand, most freshwater sequences appeared in two clades that were
219 already described from Lake George, one of them (LG Heterokonta I) contained
220 exclusively environmental sequences. Several cultured strains formed long branches
221 without a clear position and no environmental representation.

222 The phylogenetic and novelty analyses could be combined to display the
223 novelty of each clade as its position in the CEM/CCM plot based on the averaged
224 values for all environmental sequences, and the relevance of the clade by sizing the
225 dot proportionally to the number of sequences (Fig. 6). It is interesting to note the
226 distinct placement of each clade within the plotted area. For instance the four new
227 chrysophyte clades (G to J) and the two new choanoflagellate clades (D and E) all
228 appeared below the diagonal revealing higher similarity with CEM than with CCM,

229 confirming the environmental origin of its sequences. Another interesting case were
230 the bicosoecid clades, all distributing along the diagonal, with extreme novelty
231 displayed by the LG Heterokonta I clade.

232

233 **Discussion**

234 This study is an effort to analyze the data existing in environmental molecular
235 surveys for three protist groups, chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and bicosoecids,
236 which are often observed in aquatic samples and thought to account for a significant
237 fraction of heterotrophic flagellates (Arndt et al. 2000; Patterson and Lee 2000).

238 There is little doubt that sequencing of environmental clones offers an enhanced view
239 of in situ diversity for very small protists (Caron et al. 2004; Jürgens and Massana
240 2008). Environmental sequences highlight the dominant members of natural
241 assemblages and may reveal new and unexpected lineages. We do not assume that
242 the data analyzed here do not face methodological limitations. PCR-based clone
243 libraries suffer a variety of drawbacks that have been discussed in detail (von
244 Wintzingerode et al. 1997). Also, different microbial size fractions were analyzed in
245 each study (see Table S1), potentially biasing against protists from certain size
246 classes. In addition, intrinsic differences may occur between marine and freshwater
247 environments, with freshwater systems being generally less homogeneous and
248 undersampled as compared with marine systems. Nevertheless, our analysis clearly
249 identified new diversity and reduced the knowledge gaps within these groups. We
250 provide a snapshot of the novelty of the groups that will change in the future
251 depending on the effort of their study.

252 We first estimated the relative clonal abundance of chrysophytes,
253 choanoflagellates and bicosoecids with respect to other groups of putative
254 heterotrophic flagellates. This exercise should not be translated into absolute
255 abundances, but instead used for a relative comparison among groups. In marine
256 systems, only 5% of clones belonged to chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and
257 bicosoecids, a low number given that these groups were proposed to account for
258 most of the marine heterotrophic flagellates (Arndt et al, 2000; Patterson and Lee
259 2000; Brandt and Sleight 2000), and in contrast with the large clonal abundance of
260 the marine uncultured MAST or MALV (Massana and Pedrós-Alió, 2008). This
261 contribution could still be lower, since a fraction of environmental chrysophyte
262 sequences could derive from chlorophyll-containing cells (Fuller et al. 2006). Also,
263 half of the studies analyze small protists (Supplementary Table 1) and in these
264 samples the contribution of choanoflagellates could have been underestimated, since
265 these cells are usually larger than 3-5 μm and some are covered by a mineral lorica.
266 However, choanoflagellates are thought to be less abundant than stramenopile
267 flagellates (Arndt et al. 2000; Brandt and Sleight, 2000), although they may reach up
268 to 20% of the heterotrophic flagellates in polar systems (Leakey et al. 2002). A very
269 different situation occurs in freshwater systems, where bicosoecids represent 22%
270 and chrysophytes 12% of clonal abundance, matching the importance given to these
271 organisms in freshwater systems (Carrias et al. 1998; Arndt et al. 2000).

272 The estimates of relative clonal abundance suggested that chrysophytes,
273 choanoflagellates and bicosoecids might be less important than expected in marine
274 systems. The presence of these three groups was independently assessed by the

275 analysis of GOS metagenomes (Rusch et al. 2007), which were built by sequencing
276 the environmental DNA directly, and so were free of PCR biases. From the 115
277 sequences of eukaryotic 18S rDNA retrieved from all samples (Not et al. 2009), only
278 one affiliated with choanoflagellates and two to chrysophytes. As comparison, other
279 groups such as MAST or MALV were much more represented in the GOS
280 metagenomes (15 and 36 sequences, respectively). This PCR-independent
281 approach does not give a definitive answer, either, since it could be strongly affected
282 by the variable copy number of the rDNA operon in different taxa (Zhu et al., 2005).
283 To validate the cell abundance of chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and bicosoecids in
284 the marine plankton, quantitative methods such as FISH (or quantitative-PCR with
285 the proper controls) are needed.

286 We propose a new approach (Massana et al. 2010) to address the novelty of a
287 given dataset based on the similarity against GenBank sequences. Overall, the
288 novelty displayed by the environmental sequences of each group was rather large,
289 and this was interpreted in terms of efforts in culturing and environmental
290 sequencing. In our context the correspondence of environmental sequences with
291 sequences derived from cultures means that ecologically relevant protists have been
292 cultured. It combines the culturing effort with the ability of a given taxa to grow in the
293 laboratory. In our dataset, such correspondence was apparent only in a few cases,
294 like in marine bicosoecids. A low correspondence between environmental sequences
295 and sequences obtained from cultures was the more common situation, being
296 extreme for freshwater bicosoecids and choanoflagellates whose environmental
297 sequences only shared 91% similarity with CCM. Enhanced efforts and novel

298 culturing strategies will be needed to bring more ecologically relevant (i.e. abundant)
299 protists into culture, in a similar manner that has been so successful with dominant
300 marine prokaryotes (Könneke et al. 2005; Rappé et al. 2002).

301 On the other hand, sequencing environmental DNA is relatively straightforward
302 and there are little chances to miss quantitatively important major phylogenetic
303 groups. An insufficient sequencing effort was generally found in our study, with low
304 averaged similarity values of our target sequences against those from other
305 molecular surveys. In addition, similarities against CCM and CEM for different
306 sequence sets were rather similar (Table 1), with the exception of marine
307 chrysophytes for which sequencing was decreasing the novelty. This suggests that
308 there is plenty of room to discover additional diversity for these groups using
309 environmental molecular surveys, which should also take advantage of new high-
310 throughput sequencing technologies (Amaral-Zettler et al. 2009; Stoeck et al. 2009)
311 or use group-specific primers (Bass and Cavalier-Smith 2004). Alternatively, another
312 explanation for low similarity with CEM would be a large endemism of the studied
313 sequences, which might appear only in the studied site. At any rate, our novelty
314 analysis showed that the three protists groups studied here (except marine
315 bicosoecids) need further sequencing effort to reach a full understanding of the in situ
316 diversity.

317 Our use of environmental sequences from public databases improved the
318 chrysophyte, choanoflagellate and bicosoecid phylogeny and identified emergent
319 new diversity. Thus, four novel clades appeared within chrysophytes, two within
320 choanoflagellates and one within bicosoecids. The tree topologies and clade

321 divisions promise to be very useful as a backbone reference for future studies. An
322 interesting observation from the bicosoecid and choanoflagellate trees was the
323 appearance of a single monophyletic freshwater clade nested within several marine
324 clades. This could be a sign of a single and perhaps ancient transition event from
325 marine to freshwater systems in both protist groups (Logares et al. 2009). In marine
326 systems, chrysophytes harbored an important new diversity, suggesting that
327 uncultured chrysophytes, unlike the easily cultured *Spumella* or *Paraphysomonas*,
328 may be ecologically more relevant (Lim et al. 1999). The same applied for marine
329 choanoflagellates, which showed a great discrepancy between their representation in
330 culture and their abundance in clone libraries. In contrast, marine bicosoecids were
331 highly similar to cultured organisms. Finally, the three groups contained a significant
332 hidden diversity in freshwater systems, specially bicosoecids and choanoflagellates.

333 In summary, our culture-independent analysis highlighted a large diversity of
334 chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and bicosoecids in aquatic environments that was
335 accompanied with a high novelty degree. This indicated a bias in the representation
336 of cultures and an incomplete sequencing effort for these groups. This analysis
337 should be extended to other protist groups in order to fully benefit from environmental
338 molecular surveys (Marin & Melkonian 2010). Increasing the effort of environmental
339 sequencing of aquatic protists is already on the research agenda of several
340 laboratories worldwide (Amaral-Zettler et al. 2009; Stoeck et al. 2009). On the other
341 hand, it is equally important to increase the culturing efforts, to match the diversity of
342 protist cultures with the in situ diversity of ecologically relevant protists. Besides
343 culturing efforts, other techniques such as FISH should be applied to assess the

344 abundance and ecological role of new taxa (Chambouvet et al. 2008; Massana et al.
345 2006). The extent of environmental diversity and novelty is striking even for protist
346 groups that were considered well characterized.

347

348 **Methods**

349 **Sequence dataset retrieval:** Environmental 18S rDNA sequences of
350 chrysophytes, choanoflagellates and bicosoecids were obtained from GenBank in a
351 two-step screening. First, sequences found by the NCBI Taxonomy Application were
352 retrieved and checked by BLAST (Altschul et al. 1997) to confirm their placement.
353 Second, we used these and other published sequences from cultures or
354 environmental surveys that belong to the target groups (but are not labeled as such
355 in GenBank) to retrieve additional sequences by BLAST. Putative chimeric
356 sequences were checked by KeyDNATools (www.keydnatools.com) as described
357 before (Guillou et al. 2008). Neighbor Joining phylogenetic trees (see later) were
358 constructed with wide taxon coverage to find out whether or not ambiguous divergent
359 sequences belong to a given group. Related sequences from cultured organisms
360 were also retrieved from GenBank and pruned to keep only a few representatives for
361 phylogeny.

362 Two 18S rDNA clone libraries were constructed from dark unamended
363 incubations done in March 2006 and October 2007 with Blanes Bay (Mediterranean
364 Sea) seawater prefiltered by a 3 µm filter. These incubations are known to promote
365 the growth of uncultured HF (Massana et al. 2006). Picoplanktonic biomass was

366 collected on filters, and community DNA was extracted. Complete 18S rDNA genes
367 were PCR amplified with eukaryote-specific primers, and the PCR products were
368 cloned. Details of the filtering setup, DNA extraction protocol, and PCR and cloning
369 conditions are described elsewhere (Massana et al. 2004, 2006). Twenty-five and 44
370 clones were partially sequenced with the primer 528f by the MACROGEN Genomics
371 Sequencing Services. Sequences were identified and inspected for chimeras by
372 BLAST and KeyDNATools, yielding 18 target sequences (accession numbers
373 HQ437173 – HQ437184 and HQ437193 – HQ437196). Ten clones from these
374 libraries and from published libraries (BL in Massana et al. 2004; IND in Not et al.
375 2008) were completely sequenced with five internal primers by the same service. The
376 final sequence dataset consisted in 395 complete or partial environmental sequences
377 from the three target groups.

378 **Novelty analysis:** To infer the novelty of an environmental sequence dataset,
379 we noted for each sequence its similarity in a BLAST search with the closest
380 environmental match (CEM) and the closest cultured match (CCM). The CEM is the
381 first sequence in the output that derives from a molecular survey (excluding those
382 from the same library), and the CCM is the first sequence in the output that belongs
383 to a known organism (often cultured). Both similarity values for all sequences are
384 plotted in a 2D dispersion graph, giving the "novelty pattern" of the dataset. Dots with
385 high CCM similarity (i.e. above 98%) represent environmental sequences close to
386 cultured organisms, whereas dots with low CCM similarity (i.e. below 94%) highlight
387 environmental sequences with no cultured counterpart. Conversely, sequences with
388 high CEM similarity indicate an optimal sequencing effort (they have been found in

389 other environmental surveys), and those with low CEM similarity highlight an
390 insufficient sequencing effort. Finally, the "novelty degree" of the dataset is obtained
391 by averaging the similarity values for all sequences.

392 **Phylogenetic analyses:** 18S rDNA sequences were aligned using MAFFT
393 (Kato et al. 2002) using a close relative as out-group. Alignments were checked
394 with Seaview 3.2 (Galtier et al. 1996) and highly variable regions of the alignment
395 were removed using Gblocks (Castresana 2000). Neighbor Joining trees were first
396 done with PAUP 4.0b10 (Swofford 2002) with all partial sequences in order to define
397 all possible diversity, and to assure that each clade has at least one clone with the
398 complete sequence. Then, Maximum likelihood (ML) phylogenetic trees with
399 complete sequences were constructed with the fast ML method RAxML (Stamatakis
400 2006) using the evolutionary model GTRMIXI. Phylogenetic analyses were done in
401 the freely available University of Oslo Bioportal (www.bioportal.uio.no). Repeated
402 runs on distinct starting trees were carried out to select the tree with the best
403 topology (the one having the best Likelihood of 1000 alternative trees). Bootstrap ML
404 analysis was done with 1000 pseudo-replicates and the consensus tree was
405 computed with MrBayes (Huelsenbeck and Ronquist 2001). Trees were edited with
406 FigTree v1.3.1 (<http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/figtree/>).

407

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415

416 **Appendix A. Supplementary material**

417 Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at
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419

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569

569 **Table. 1.** Novelty degree represented by environmental sequences of chrysophytes,
570 choanoflagellates and bicosoecids. In this integrated analysis we show the average
571 similarity (standard error in brackets) with closest environmental match (CEM) and
572 closest cultured match (CCM) for all sequences separated by environments and
573 together. The second column shows to the number of sequences analyzed and the
574 last column the statistical tests (*** : $p < 0.0001$, ns: not significant).
575

	Environment	n	% CEM (SE)	% CCM (SE)	t-student
Chrysophytes	Marine	144	97.6 (0.2)	94.2 (0.3)	***
	Freshwater	86	95.3 (0.3)	95.8 (0.3)	ns
	All	230	96.8 (0.2)	94.8 (0.2)	***
Choanoflagellates	Marine	69	95.3 (0.3)	94.7 (0.4)	ns
	Freshwater	20	90.8 (0.5)	91.6 (0.7)	ns
	All	89	94.3 (0.3)	94.0 (0.3)	ns
Bicosoecids	Marine	45	98.1 (0.4)	98.3 (0.5)	ns
	Freshwater	31	90.9 (0.4)	90.6 (0.6)	ns
	All	76	95.1 (0.3)	95.0 (0.4)	ns

576

576 **Figure legends**

577 **Figure 1.** Relative clonal abundance of different taxonomic groups putatively forming
578 the heterotrophic flagellate assemblages in marine and freshwater systems (data
579 from 82 clone libraries of 18S rDNA genes; see Supplementary Table 3).

580 **Figure 2.** Novelty pattern derived from chrysophyte (A), choanoflagellate (B) and
581 bicosoecid (C) environmental sequences. Dots represent the % similarity with the
582 closest environmental match (CEM) and the closest cultured match (CCM) for each
583 sequence within the three taxa (229, 88, and 76 sequences, respectively) and are
584 colored depending the environment where they originate (dark: marine; light:
585 freshwater).

586 **Figure 3.** Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree of chrysophytes constructed with
587 270 complete 18S rDNA sequences (1648 informative positions). Sequences from
588 cultured taxa appear in black and environmental sequences appear in blue (marine)
589 or green (freshwater). ML bootstrap values are shown for the named clades. The
590 number of complete and partial environmental sequences assigned to each clade
591 appear after the clade name. The scale bar indicates 0.1 substitutions per position.

592 **Figure 4.** Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree of choanoflagellates constructed
593 with 79 complete 18S rDNA sequences (1428 informative positions). Legend as in
594 Fig. 3.

595 **Figure 5.** Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree of bicosoecids constructed with 66
596 complete 18S rDNA sequences (1485 informative positions). Legend as in Fig. 3.

597 **Figure 6.** Novelty pattern derived from each described clade within chrysophytes (**A**),
598 choanoflagellates (**B**) and bicosoecids (**C**). Dots representing the novelty of the
599 clades (average similarity against CEM and CCM for all environmental sequences
600 within the clade) have a size proportional to the number of sequences. Different grey
601 tones are used for convenience.